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Trust in Parliament in the Italian Regions

It increased by 31.15% between 2011 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of trust in parliament in the Italian regions. Trust in parliament is defined as the average score of trust in the Italian Parliament - on a scale from 0 to 10 - expressed by people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period between 2011 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of trust in parliament in the Italian regions in 2022. Lazio and Campania are in first place by value of trust in parliament in the Italian regions in 2022 with a value equal to 4.9 units followed by Puglia with a value of 4.8 units. In the middle of the table are Molise, Basilicata and Sicily with a value of 4.6 units. Veneto closes the ranking with a value of 4.2 units followed by Valle d'Aosta and Sardinia with a value of 4 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in trust in parliament between 2011 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place by value of the change in trust in parliament between 2011 and 2022 with a value of 46.88% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.2 units up to 4.7 units or equal to an amount of 1.5 units. Lazio and Campania follow with a variation equal to 40.00% corresponding to a variation from 3.5 units up to 4.9 units. In the middle of the table there is Puglia with a value equal to +33.33% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.6 units up to a value of 4.8 units. Piedmont and Veneto follow with a variation equal to 31.25% corresponding to a variation from 3.2 units up to 4.2 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with a value equal to +24.32% corresponding to a variation from 3.7 units up to 4.6 units equal to 0.9 units. Lombardy follows with a value of 22.86% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.5 units up to 4.3 units corresponding to an amount of 0.8 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a value of +14.29% corresponding to a variation from 3.5 units up to 4 units. Overall, the value of trust in parliament grew from an amount of 3.44 units up to an amount of 4.51 units or equal to a value of 31.15%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The following clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Liguria, Puglia, Lazio, Campania, Calabria, Basilicata, Tuscany, Molise, Abruzzo, Emilia Romagna, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Sardinia, Trentino Alto Adige, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Sicily, Piedmont.

From the point of view of the value of the average of the clusters it is possible to identify the following ordering of the clusters, that is: Cluster 1 > Cluster 2. Specifically we can verify that Cluster 1 is made up of almost all the southern regions with the exception of Sardinia and Sicily, and from some regions of the central north. Both clusters are quite heterogeneous even if Cluster 1 is certainly dominated by the presence of the southern regions.

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Trust in the Italian parliament in Italian macro-regions. We can note that the value of trust in the Italian parliament grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. Specifically, trust in the Italian parliament in the Italian macro-regions grew in the North by 26.47%, in the North -West of 26.47%, in the North-East of 33.33%, in the Center of 37.14%, in the South of 34.29%, in Southern Italy of 37.14%, in the Islands for a value of 36 ,36%. We can note that the maximum levels of trust in parliament are reached in the macro-regions of Central and Southern Italy.

That is, trust in parliament tends to be inversely proportional to per capita income. The areas of the country characterized by a reduced capacity to produce per capita income are also the same ones that have high levels of trust in parliament. Probably the regions that have greater capacity to generate gross domestic product also have greater autonomy in social action and therefore do not feel the need to place trust in institutions. On the contrary, it is probable that in the northern regions with a high level of per capita income there exists a sort of distrust towards the State and public action, as is well represented by a series of political movements and autonomist demands. On the contrary, the southern regions with reduced per capita income and with a level of private initiative among the population that is certainly lower than that of the regions of Northern Italy, experience higher levels of trust in parliament. It is probable that in this different distribution of trust in parliament between the North and the South there is also a component of institutional and political culture. In fact, Northern Italy has traditionally always been oriented by a certain importance of local institutions and autonomies as represented by the civilization of the municipalities and lordships. A phenomenon absolutely absent within the southern regions, less accustomed to the idea of autonomism and federalism and more prone to a centralized power structure. However, it is very likely that this distinction also contains the failure of the republican objective of reducing the gaps between North and South, not only from an economic, political and cultural point of view, but also from the point of view of institutional participation. After more than 150 years of unitary history and more than 70 years of a republican constitution, it is certainly possible to affirm that the objective of eliminating the North-South divide has completely failed. And indeed, it is possible to demonstrate that, especially in recent years, inequality has continued to grow. And the distribution of trust in public institutions, which tends to grow as income decreases, is further proof of this.

Conclusions. Between 2011 and 2022 the value of trust in parliament grew in all Italian regions. The data shows that the southern regions tend to have greater trust in parliament with the exception of Sardinia and Sicily. It is likely that the fact that Sardinia and Sicily are regions with special status could reduce trust in parliament in favor of greater effectiveness of the special regional system. In general, trust in parliament grows with the reduction in per capita income.

References

- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.
- Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. *Available at SSRN 3964059*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. *Available at SSRN 3933553*.
- Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Determinants of CO2 Emissions in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4425121*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4420946*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Fight Against Corruption at Global Level. A Metric Approach. *A Metric Approach (December 30, 2022)*.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022, February). Use of machine learning to predict the glycemic status of patients with diabetes. In *Medical Sciences Forum* (Vol. 10, No. 1, p. 11). MDPI.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3930697*.

Laureti, L., Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Renewable Electricity Output on Sustainability in the Context of Circular Economy: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2160.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2021). Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction. *Machine Learning and Prediction* (September 29, 2021). *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

MAGAZZINO, C., & LEOGRANDE, A. (2021). Subjective Well-Being In Italian Regions: A Panel Data Approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJISSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR) e-ISSN*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.*

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3933407.*

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Leogrande, D., & Anobile, F. (2023). Beds in Health Facilities in the Italian Regions: A Socio-Economic Approach. *Available at SSRN 4577029.*

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016.*

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755.*

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232.*

Appendix

Macro-regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	3,4	3,5	3,1	3,3	3,3	3,5	3,3	3,8	4,4	4,4	4,5	4,3
Nord-ovest	3,4	3,6	3,2	3,4	3,3	3,6	3,4	3,8	4,4	4,4	4,5	4,3
Nord-est	3,3	3,4	3	3,2	3,2	3,4	3,2	3,7	4,3	4,4	4,4	4,4
Centro	3,5	3,6	3,3	3,7	3,6	3,8	3,6	3,9	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,8
Mezzogiorno	3,5	3,6	3,4	3,6	3,5	3,8	3,3	3,8	4,6	4,6	4,7	4,7
Sud	3,5	3,8	3,5	3,7	3,6	3,9	3,5	4	4,7	4,8	4,8	4,8
Isole	3,3	3,4	3,2	3,4	3,2	3,5	3	3,5	4,4	4,3	4,5	4,5
Italia	3,4	3,6	3,3	3,5	3,4	3,7	3,4	3,8	4,5	4,5	4,6	4,5

Regione	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	3,2	3,6	3,2	3,5	3,3	3,6	3,2	3,7	4,4	4,5	4,6	4,2
Valle d'Aosta	3,5	3,3	2,9	3	3,2	3,4	3,2	3,4	4,1	4,3	4,1	4
Liguria	3,7	4	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,8	3,6	4,1	4,5	4,8	4,6	4,6
Lombardia	3,5	3,6	3,1	3,3	3,2	3,5	3,4	3,9	4,4	4,3	4,4	4,3
Trentino-Alto Adige	3,2	3,4	2,9	3,2	3,4	3,5	3,7	3,5	4,3	4,3	4,4	4,3
Veneto	3,2	3,3	2,7	2,8	2,9	3,1	2,8	3,6	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2

<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	3,5	3,5	2,9	3,5	3,2	3,5	3,5	3,9	4,3	4,2	4,3	4,4
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	3,4	3,5	3,4	3,5	3,4	3,7	3,4	3,7	4,4	4,6	4,7	4,7
<i>Toscana</i>	3,4	3,5	3,4	3,9	3,7	3,8	3,6	3,9	4,6	4,6	4,7	4,7
<i>Umbria</i>	3,5	3,6	3	3,3	3,2	3,6	3,4	4	4,6	4,7	4,7	4,5
<i>Marche</i>	3,5	3,3	3,2	3,1	3,3	3,6	3	3,8	4,5	4,4	4,4	4,4
<i>Lazio</i>	3,5	3,8	3,4	3,7	3,7	3,8	3,7	4	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,9
<i>Abruzzo</i>	3,2	3,9	3,6	3,4	3,3	3,6	3,3	3,6	4,7	4,7	4,6	4,7
<i>Molise</i>	3,6	3,8	3,4	3,5	3,3	3,4	3,1	4	4,5	4,8	4,7	4,6
<i>Campania</i>	3,5	3,8	3,5	4	3,7	4,2	3,6	4,1	4,7	4,8	4,9	4,9
<i>Puglia</i>	3,6	3,7	3,5	3,5	3,7	3,8	3,4	3,9	4,9	4,7	4,7	4,8
<i>Basilicata</i>	3,7	4	3,4	3,3	3,8	3,7	3,6	3,8	4,7	4,7	4,6	4,6
<i>Calabria</i>	3,5	3,7	3,3	3,3	3,7	3,8	3,6	4	4,6	4,8	4,6	4,7
<i>Sicilia</i>	3,4	3,5	3,3	3,5	3,3	3,7	3,1	3,6	4,5	4,3	4,6	4,6
<i>Sardegna</i>	3,1	3,1	3	3	2,8	3	2,9	3,2	4,3	4,3	4,2	4

Rank	Regione	2022
1	Lazio	4,9
2	Campania	4,9
3	Puglia	4,8
4	Emilia-Romagna	4,7
5	Toscana	4,7
6	Abruzzo	4,7
7	Calabria	4,7
8	Liguria	4,6
9	Molise	4,6
10	Basilicata	4,6
11	Sicilia	4,6
12	Umbria	4,5
13	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	4,4
14	Marche	4,4
15	Lombardia	4,3
16	Trentino-Alto Adige	4,3
17	Piemonte	4,2
18	Veneto	4,2
19	Valle d'Aosta	4
20	Sardegna	4

